

Digitizing and Structuring Early Marine Biodiversity Records: A GraphRAG-Based Methodology

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Abstract. This work presents a method for generating and refining a knowledge graph (KG) from a historically significant 20th-century marine biology text. The source, a foundational ecological survey, was digitized using OCR and processed for semantic consistency. Knowledge extraction was performed with GraphRAG and the GPT-4o-mini model, producing an initial KG with verbose and inconsistent relationships. To improve clarity and alignment with semantic web standards, a two-step refinement process was applied, combining automated tuning and prompt engineering. The result was a set of concise, RDF-style predicates suitable for querying and integration with ontological frameworks. The refined KG is accessible via a public platform supporting multilingual natural language queries, enabling broader use of historical ecological data. This approach highlights the potential of AI-assisted pipelines to transform legacy scientific texts into semantically structured, interoperable resources for biodiversity research.

Keywords: Open Knowledge Graphs · GraphRAG · Large Language Models · Natural Language Queries · Digital Knowledge Preservation

1 Introduction

Digitizing historical marine science literature enhances accessibility [9], but structuring it into semantically rich formats remains challenging. Extracting knowledge from unstructured texts often produces verbose or inconsistent relations, hindering reasoning and queries.

Knowledge Graphs (KGs) provide a robust framework to model scientific data by explicitly capturing entities and relationships [5]. Projects like OBIS [11] and OceanGraph [17] integrate modern marine biodiversity and oceanographic data,

but lack methods to refine relations extracted from historical texts, which suffer from linguistic variability and OCR noise.

Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) [7] combines information retrieval with large language models (LLMs) [15] to support knowledge-intensive tasks using structured data. GraphRAG extends this by integrating graph-based retrieval with LLMs to generate graph representations [13]. However, when applied to historical marine biology texts, it often yields overly long predicates and inconsistent naming, limiting semantic interoperability.

In this work, we propose a methodology to extract and refine a marine science KG from a digitized historical text using GraphRAG library [3]. Our contributions are fourfold:

- **Text digitization:** OCR and cleaning pipelines convert scanned Spanish texts into structured, multilingual formats.
- **Graph construction:** Using GPT-4o-mini via OpenAI API, we extract entities and relationships from the processed text.
- **Relationship refinement:** A two-phase process (autotuning and prompt engineering) yields concise, RDF-style predicates.
- **Evaluation:** We assess improvements in predicate length, semantic alignment with standard RDF terms, and query retrieval accuracy.

By refining extracted relationships into semantically precise formats, our approach enhances the coherence and usability of KGs derived from historical marine texts. This work advances the integration of ontologies, KGs, and LLMs, providing a reproducible pipeline that supports both researchers and non-experts in exploring marine biodiversity and ecological interactions through natural language interfaces. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2, presents the State of the Art. Section 3, details the Methodology. Section 4, discusses the Results, Section 5, provides the Conclusion and outlines Future Work and Section 6, for acknowledgements.

2 State of the Art

KGs are vital for organizing and integrating complex scientific data, including marine sciences [16]. By formally modeling entities (e.g., species, habitats) and their relationships, KGs enable semantic interoperability across datasets. Systems like OBIS [11] aggregate structured species occurrence data globally but exclude unstructured texts. OceanGraph [17] uses ontologies to harmonize taxonomic, observational, and environmental data, illustrating KGs’ potential for interoperable marine knowledge. Beyond oceanography, KGs support operational uses such as the Maritime Accident Knowledge Graph (MAKG) [8], which formalizes unstructured incident reports for semantic search and decision support. While valuable, these rely on curated datasets and schemas, limiting applicability to unstructured or historical sources. Advances in NLP introduced methods like RAG, combining retrieval with LLMs, grounding outputs in relevant data.

GraphRAG enhances this by leveraging KGs as retrieval backends, improving relevance, consistency, and explainability [7,1,14]. Nevertheless, extracting coherent relations from unstructured text remains difficult due to ambiguous predicates. This work proposes a methodology using GraphRAG with a two-phase optimization—automated tuning and prompt engineering—to produce concise RDF-style labels, enhancing KG usability and interoperability from legacy texts.

3 Methodology

This section describes the methodology, from text digitization to KG construction and refinement using GraphRAG. Emphasis is placed on optimizing extracted relationships to ensure concise, semantically coherent, RDF-aligned connections, enhancing usability for natural language queries and improving retrieval and interpretability.

Fig. 1. From Book to KG: This workflow illustrates the transformation of a physical book into a refined KG using Microsoft GraphRAG, enabling natural language queries through a web interface.

3.1 Text Digitization

The source text used in this study is the historical book *Lobos marinos, pingüinos y guaneras de las costas del litoral marítimo e islas adyacentes de la República Argentina*, authored by Italo Santiago Carrara and published in 1952 by the Ministry of Education of the Universidad Nacional de La Plata [2]. This work is one of the earliest and most comprehensive surveys of marine vertebrate fauna along the Argentine coast, including both mainland shores and adjacent islands. Its scientific value lies in its detailed biological descriptions of pinnipeds and seabirds, covering aspects like reproductive cycles, feeding habits, parasitic profiles, and population structures, as well as its insights into industrial activities related to guano exploitation and marine resource use.

Given its role as a key historical reference for marine ecology in Argentina, digitizing this volume was a necessary step toward preserving and analyzing legacy ecological knowledge. The book existed only in print, with no digital or machine-readable version available in biodiversity systems.

Text extraction was performed via high-resolution scanning and OCR, following the method in [10], optimized for Spanish scientific texts. Post-processing included de-noising, segmentation, artifact removal, and structural formatting to preserve semantic accuracy.

Despite being originally in Spanish, the digitized content now supports multilingual access through language models with cross-lingual capabilities, enhancing global accessibility and enabling broader interaction with historical marine ecological data.

3.2 KG Generation with GraphRAG

To construct the KG, we employed GraphRAG, a framework designed to extract structured knowledge from unstructured text. Our approach integrated the OpenAI API with the GPT-4o-mini model [12], optimized for natural language understanding and semantic knowledge extraction. This setup enabled the identification of key entities—such as species, habitats, and ecological interactions—and their relationships within a structured graph.

The initial KG successfully captured relevant entities but exhibited inconsistencies in relationship representations. Many extracted relationships were overly verbose, often exceeding 30 words, making them difficult to interpret and integrate with standard knowledge representation frameworks. Additionally, the lack of uniformity in naming conventions introduced ambiguities that could complicate automated reasoning and query execution.

To address these issues, we refined the extracted relationships by restructuring them into concise, RDF-style formats, improving clarity and interpretability while ensuring alignment with established ontological models. The optimization process—detailed in the following section—included both automated refinements through GraphRAG’s tuning capabilities and manual adjustments via prompt engineering, ensuring semantically meaningful and standardized connections.

3.3 Graph Tuning and Optimization

The tuning process was carried out in two complementary phases:

1. **Autotuning with GraphRAG:** We initially leveraged GraphRAG’s built-in autotuning mechanisms to optimize entity extraction and relationship linking. This automated approach allowed us to adjust the parameters of the model to enhance the overall structure of the graph, ensuring that the most relevant concepts were identified and linked correctly.
2. **Refinement through Prompt Engineering:** While autotuning laid a solid foundation for the KG, further refinements were needed to improve precision and clarity in the extracted relationships. We manually adjusted GraphRAG prompts, prioritizing concise relationships over lengthy ones. This refinement ensured the relationships aligned with the Resource Description Framework (RDF) [6], enhancing the KG’s coherence and integration with ontologies and improving query efficiency.

3.4 Evaluation and Validation

To assess the impact of the tuning process, we focus on evaluating the refinement of relationships within the KG. Initially, we observed that many extracted relationships were overly descriptive rather than adhering to the concise and standardized structure typically found in RDF-based representations. To address this, we applied prompt tuning to encourage the generation of shorter, semantically precise relationships.

The evaluation process consists of the following steps:

- **Comparison of relationship length:** We analyze the average length (in words or characters) of the relationships before and after tuning, expecting a reduction in verbosity and an alignment with RDF-style structures.
- **Structural assessment:** We classify relationships into two categories: descriptive (long-form explanations) and structured (short RDF-like predicates). A reduction in descriptive relationships post-tuning indicates improvement adherence to semantic web standards.
- **Alignment with expected relations:** A predefined set of standard RDF-style relations (e.g., “located in”, “part of”, “feeds on”) serves as a reference. We measure how many of the generated relationships match these expected formats before and after tuning.
- **Qualitative analysis:** We manually examine a subset of extracted relationships to verify that post-tuning outputs are more precise, meaningful, and aligned with domain-specific ontologies.

Similar approaches using transformer-based models to assess the authenticity or quality of text have demonstrated the viability of using quantitative metrics, such as F1-score, in semantic extraction and classification tasks [4].

The following table compares the relationships extracted before and after the tuning process, highlighting improvements in conciseness, semantic precision, and alignment with RDF-style representations.

4 Results and Discussion

As presented in Table 1, the tuning process improved the structural quality of the knowledge graph (KG) by aligning extracted relationships with RDF-style formats. This enabled clearer domain representation and more accurate entity connections. Descriptive phrases were refined into concise, standardized predicates—e.g., “life event” and “survival behavior” for maternal care and defense instincts, and “inhabits” or “subcategory of” for location and taxonomy. This addressed issues of verbosity and inconsistency often found in GraphRAG outputs from historical texts. Integrating this refined knowledge into RAG systems enhances semantic consistency and interpretability. Nonetheless, the KG’s quality still depends on early processing steps like OCR and entity extraction, where initial errors may propagate. These findings highlight prompt tuning as an effective strategy for converting unstructured historical data into structured, semantically rich resources suitable for AI-driven biodiversity research.

Table 1. Evaluation of relation transformations before and after prompt tuning, measuring alignment with RDF-style formats.

From Entity	To Entity	Relation Before Tuning	Relation After Tuning
Mother	Birth	“Birth marks the beginning of maternal care and care of the offspring”	“life event”
Pup	Defense instinct	“The pup shows defense instincts just a few hours after birth, trying to break free when handled”	“survival behavior”
Elephant seal	Colony	“The elephant seal colony consists of a few individuals of both sexes on the coasts”	“inhabits”
South American sea lion	Otaria flavescens	“Otaria flavescens is the scientific name of the South American sea lion, which describes its taxonomic classification”	“subcategory of”

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This study introduced a methodology for extracting and refining structured knowledge from historical marine biology texts using GraphRAG. By digitizing *Lobos marinos, pingüinos y guaneras de las costas del litoral marítimo e islas adyacentes de la República Argentina* [2]—a foundational work surveying Argentina’s coastal marine fauna—we demonstrated how legacy literature can be transformed into a reusable, semantically coherent KG.

Our pipeline combined OCR digitization, language model-driven knowledge extraction, and a two-phase refinement process based on autotuning and prompt engineering. This approach produced concise, RDF-style relationships, improving the interpretability and query performance of the resulting graph.

We also developed an open-access platform for natural language interaction with the digitized content, platform: <https://bio-bot.cenpat-conicet.gob.ar/>, repository: <https://github.com/gustavomarcelonunez/oceangraphrag>

Future work includes extending the methodology to additional historical sources, integrating external ontologies, and evaluating the system with expert users. We also plan to explore quantitative evaluation methods, such as precision, recall, and F1-score, using curated reference data. This contribution highlights the potential of hybrid AI methods for preserving and operationalizing historical scientific knowledge in biodiversity research.

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